

THERMAL CYCLING BEHAVIOR OF AN Al-7Si-3Cu-15% SAFFIL SHORT FIBER METAL MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The thermal cycling behavior of a squeeze-cast Al-7Si-3Cu reinforced with 15% Saffil δ -Al₂O₃ short fibers has been investigated. The effects of number of thermal cycles (N) and maximum temperature (T_{\max}) were studied at 250, 350 and 450°C with a minimum temperature T_{\min} at 100°C. It was shown that the roughness of the free surface increased with both T_{\max} and N. Transient and steady-state regimes were observed in the roughness vs. N curves. The dislocation microstructures as well as the evolution of the precipitates state were studied by TEM for all T_{\max} at 1250 thermal cycles. It is emphasized that the dislocation arrangements and precipitating state can alter the amount of surface roughening.

Keywords : MMC, thermal fatigue, thermal cycling, Al-7Si-3Cu, dislocation, precipitating state, roughness, surface stability

1. INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) are promising new advanced materials for replacing existing alloys in certain applications. Higher wear resistance and mechanical strength as well as higher specific stiffness at elevated temperature are among the properties required for MMC use [1]. It is well recognized that because of the difference between the thermal expansion of the matrix and the reinforcement, MMCs are prone to micro and macrostructural damage when subjected to thermal cycling (TC) [1,2]. The surface changes of MMCs during TC [3, 4] is of great importance in applications where dimensional stability and wear resistance properties are required.

The objective of this work was to investigate the TC behavior of a precipitate hardenable aluminium base alloy, Al-7Si-3Cu, reinforced with 15% volume fraction of Saffil δ -Al₂O₃ short fibers. The TC behavior of this composite was compared to that of a pure aluminium matrix reinforced with the same amount of short fibers [5]. TC was performed without external loading using symmetrical heating and cooling rates. The effects of T_{\max} and N were both studied and the surface roughness was quantified. The evolution of the surface structure during TC was studied by SEM. A brief examination of the microstructural changes of dislocation arrangements and precipitating state was performed by means of transmission electron microscopy (TEM).

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The microstructure of the as-received Al-7Si-3Cu (referred here as ASC) MMC reinforced with 15% δ -Al₂O₃ short fibers is shown in Figure 1. MMC blocks have been produced by Alusuisse Neuhausen-Lonza using a squeeze-casting process. Cylindrical samples of 20 mm in length and 12 mm in diameter were removed from MMC blocks by electro-discharge machining (EDM). The samples were subjected to TC in an apparatus using a high frequency induction heating system. The minimum temperature of thermal cycles (T_{\min}) was maintained at 100°C while three T_{\max} values of 250, 350 and 450°C were studied. The TC was performed with a minimum heating and cooling rate of about 5 to 9 °C/s. TC test procedures ensured the absence of the macroscopic thermal loading. Therefore, the thermal strains and subsequent thermal stresses present were only due to the difference between the coefficient of the thermal expansion (Δ CTE) of the matrix and that of the reinforcement. The details of experimental procedures and results on a pure Al matrix composite reinforced with the same amount of δ -Al₂O₃ short fibers have been given elsewhere [5].

The mean roughness (peak to valley height parameter, R_z) of pre-polished free surface of the samples were evaluated at different thermal cycles by means of a Perthen S6P perthometer. At each interruption of the test, small slices were removed from cycled samples by EDM for investigation of the surface structure by scanning electron microscopy, SEM, (Cambridge S360) and of the deformation micromechanisms of the bulk material by transmission electron microscopy, TEM, (Philips CM 20 and EM300). Only the deformation micromechanisms examined after 1250 thermal cycles are reported here.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Surface structure and roughness evolution

The effects of N and T_{\max} on the free surface structure are shown by SEM micrographs (Figure 2). These observations were made for all T_{\max} for 1250 cycles and for 50, 250 and 1250 cycles at $T_{\max}=450^\circ\text{C}$, where the effects were more noticeable. For all values of T_{\max} , the surface evolution revealed a visible rise in roughness with increasing number of thermal cycles. Although both T_{\max} and N results has shown an increase in surface roughness due to matrix plasticity, temperature appeared to be the more important factor, having more effect on surface manifestation of deformation for both ASC and pure Al [5] MMCs.

The variation of R_z with N for various T_{\max} of the ASC MMC is compared to that of the pure Al matrix composite (see Figure 3), where positive temperature and thermal cycle dependence were found. An initial transient regime and a steady-state regime were observed in R_z vs. N curves. During transient regimes, the roughness increased quite rapidly. Steady-state regimes were characterized by a linear change in roughness such that $R_z = A + B \times N$, where B corresponds to the mean roughness rate. The plot of $(\ln B)$ vs. (T_{\max}^{-1}) , shown in Figure 4, has suggested that a "thermally activated" process prevails in the roughness curve. This curve has shown a greater surface stability of ASC subjected to TC as compared to that of pure aluminium MMC. For all values of T_{\max} , the roughness rate in the steady-state regime was markedly lower for the ASC MMCs than for pure Al composite.

During the transient period at $T_{\max} = 350$ and 450°C , the R_z of the ASC composite seemed to be slightly higher than that of the pure Al matrix composite. This could have been possibly due to the effect of secondary phases (i.e., Si particles and Al₂Cu precipitates, see 3.2) that acted as reinforcement, having also a different expansion coefficient which would have increased the density of dislocation by thermal mismatch causing an increasing effect on the first cycles[6]. The scatter in R_z measurements requires additional investigation in order to adequately quantify the effect of secondary phases and dislocation structure on the transient regimes of the roughness evolution curves.

3.2. TEM OBSERVATIONS

Observations by TEM revealed that the dislocation density decreased from the fibres towards the matrix in both as-received composite [4-9], but the distribution and density of dislocations around the fibers were not quantified. Nevertheless, in ASC composite, the density of dislocations appeared to be higher and more homogeneously distributed in comparison to those seen in pure Al MMC [5], because of the presence of Si particles and in particular of the Al_2Cu precipitates in a labyrinth-shaped array, which can impede the dislocation motion (Figure 5a). Only zones free of precipitates showed the presence of tangled dislocation near the fibers.

In all the cycled ASC MMCs, EDS analysis (Figure 5d) revealed the presence of an excess of silicon as particles near the fibers (Figure 5b). These are issued from the low solubility of silicon in aluminium and are generated during the process of squeeze casting, where the Si is rejected in the last liquid around the fibers. Additionally, a thin layer of silica was visible at the surface of the fibers which came from the binder of the preform left from the squeeze casting process (see Figure 5a) as it was seen elsewhere [10].

After TC at $T_{max} = 250^\circ C$, a cellular dislocation substructure has been observed in the pure Al matrix composite following 1250 cycles [5], while in the ASC composite, such microstructural reorganization was not observed (Figure 5c). Moreover, the Al_2Cu precipitate morphology did not change during TC at this temperature. The so called "labyrinth" structure appears to have hindered the free movement of dislocations, not allowing cell structures to form and giving to the ASC composite greater microstructural stability and higher strength vis à vis the pure Al MMC.

In the ASC as in the pure Al matrix composite [5] at $T_{max} = 450^\circ C$, the cell structures were not visible. Smaller spheroidal precipitates of Al-Cu were observed at this T_{max} due to solutionizing and re-precipitation mechanisms. EDS analysis of the initial platelets, spheroidal precipitates as well as the fine precipitates found at $450^\circ C$ has shown the presence of Al and Cu (Figure 6d). Investigation is under progress in order to identify these second phases

In the bulk material, the fibers are enclosed by the matrix. In absence of external loading during TC, there is both the generation of dislocations due to the ΔCTE and simultaneously, a process of reorganization, impediment (by precipitates) and annihilation of dislocations. The density of dislocations should therefore change during TC and increase or decrease depending on whether the generation or annihilation of dislocation state prevails. Because of thermal straining, microstructural changes may occur as a function of N. For a given MMC, this microstructural change depends furthermore upon the characteristics of the thermal cycle such as T_{max} , T_{min} and heating and cooling rates. Microstructural obstacles, e.g., cells or precipitates within the matrix, can hinder dislocations movement, giving the composite a greater microstructural stability and strength.

Since the matrix at the free surface cannot enclose all the fibres, a non-equilibrium condition prevails, where dislocations tend to escape. Under this non-equilibrium condition, the microstructural evolution in the first cycles results in a transient regime in the roughening curve. In the steady state regime, loss of dislocation while heating, becomes progressively superior than the creation of dislocation after cooling and should increase, as shown by the Rz curve, with the augmentation of cycle numbers and temperature. Since the period over a temperature at which movement prevails is cumulative and long enough to permit reorganization of dislocations.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The behavior of a squeeze-cast Al-7Si-3Cu MMC reinforced with 15% volume fraction of Saffil δ -Al₂O₃ short fibers was studied under TC for various T_{max} . It was observed that the roughness of the free surface increased with both T_{max} and N . An initial transient regime, where roughness increased rapidly, and a steady-state regime characterized by a linear change in roughness, were observed in roughness evolution curves. The Al-7Si-3Cu composite revealed a higher surface stability as compared to that of the pure aluminium composite. The precipitating state of the Al-7Si-3Cu MMC and the microstructural dislocation arrangement evolved during TC. Modification of the morphology and precipitation state were observed for TC at 350 and 450°C as compared to the as-received and the $T_{max}=250^{\circ}\text{C}$ samples. Additionally, a dislocation cell structure was observed at $T_{max}=350^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1250 cycles.

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Figure 1: Microstructure of the as-received squeeze-cast Al₇Si₃Cu/15% Saffil short fibers: a) perpendicular view of the block b) plan view of the block.

Figure 2: SEM micrographs of the thermally cycled ASC MMC at $T_{\max} = 250, 350$ and 450°C for 1250 cycles; and also at $T_{\max}=450^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 50, 250 and 1250 cycles.

Figure 3: Comparison of the roughness evaluation (Rz) as a function of number of cycles (N) for ASC and pure Al MMCs.

Figure 4: Comparison of LnB as a function of the inverse of temperature for various thermal cycles for ASC and pure Al matrix MMC.

a

b

c

d

Figure 5: Transmission micrographs of ASC MMC showing:
 a) labyrinth-shaped array of Al-Cu precipitates and thin layer of silica on the fiber in as-received conditions,
 b) Si particle present on a fiber in the ASC MMC,
 c) Al-Cu precipitates after 1250 cycles, for $T_{max} = 250^{\circ}\text{C}$,
 d) EDS analysis of the Si particle shown in b).

Figure 6: Transmission micrographs of thermally cycled ASC MMCs showing:
 a) globular Al-Cu precipitates for $T_{\max} = 350^{\circ}\text{C}$,
 b) dislocation cell structure at $T_{\max} = 350^{\circ}\text{C}$,
 c) pinning of dislocations by the fine Al-Cu precipitates at $T_{\max} = 450^{\circ}\text{C}$, with absence of dislocation cell structure.
 d) EDS analysis of the precipitate in a).